

EFFECT OF PARTICULATE MATRIX INHIBITORS ON MICROSTRUCTURE AND
PROPERTIES OF 2-D CARBON-CARBON COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Extended-life applications of structural carbon-carbon (C-C) composites involve multiple periods of operation in high-temperature oxidizing environments and as such require a reliable oxidation protection system (OPS). Advanced OPS's generally consist of an external ceramic coating combined with an in-depth matrix inhibitor. This work investigated the effects produced by particulate inhibitors doped on the matrix on the microstructure of 2-D, PAN fiber-pitch matrix C-C's. Boron and zirconium-based particulate inhibitors were added to the matrix material prior to heat treatment. A process was developed to assure a uniform distribution of the inhibitors. Oxidation behavior of such matrix-inhibited composites was evaluated using isothermal oxidation tests.

KEYWORDS: Carbon-Carbon Composites; Oxidation Resistance; Matrix Inhibitors; Microstructure Characterization

1. INTRODUCTION

Carbon-carbon (C-C) composite materials are being extensively used in a variety of structural application due to their unique thermal, mechanical, and chemical properties (1). The most important of these applications require the C-C materials to operate at high-temperatures and in oxidizing environments. Unfortunately, unprotected C-C materials gasify rapidly under an oxidizing atmosphere at temperatures as low as 500°C due to CO and CO₂ formation.

Extended-life applications of C-C composites involve a considerable number of thermal cycles at temperatures below 1650°C and hundreds of operation hours. Current attempts to provide oxidation protection for C-C composites are based on incorporating an oxidation inhibitor into the C-C composite during its fabrication and then applying an external protective coating (2). The external coating encapsulates the C-C composite and serves as a primary oxygen barrier while the internal inhibitor slows down the oxidation reaction and seals the external coating cracks. The inhibitors are used both as inner coatings and matrix additives. Glass formers have been found to reduce the susceptibility of the C-C composites to oxidation when used as inhibitor additives to matrix materials (2,3). The use of glass formers rather than oxides themselves facilitates processing of the C-C composites. Glass formers result in large in-situ volume expansion when glass is formed upon exposure to oxygen and, as a consequence, glass is forced to flow into adjacent cracks and pores.

Inclusion of elemental boron or boron compounds such as zirconium boride and boron carbide within C-C material provide its in-depth oxidation protection (4). The glassy boron phase helps to close cracks formed in the outer coating, and guards against catastrophic oxidation. The inhibiting effect depends on the spreading of a viscous borate or borosilicate glassy phase within the composite structure and the C-C composite weight loss could be substantial. Nevertheless, such matrix-inhibited C-C materials have been shown to be very useful, when used in conjunction with an external protective coating such as silicon carbide (1). The presence of particulate matrix inhibitors inside composite matrices increases the complexity of densification and curing processes. In order to acquire a comprehensive understanding of the factors which affect the strength properties and oxidation resistance of these materials, thorough microstructural investigations combined with mechanical and oxidation tests are necessary. There is very little data related to the processing/property relationship for inhibited C-C composites, especially in the area of microstructural characterization (2,5).

In this paper, we present results of the first stage of the project devoted to the fabrication of inhibited pitch matrix C-C composites to be used for extended-life applications. The fabrication method employed in this research is first described followed by results of oxidation resistance tests and results of microstructural investigations of as-fabricated and oxidized specimens.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1. Materials

Matrix inhibited C-C composites presented in this work consisted of a PAN fiber reinforcement, a petroleum pitch matrix, and particulate matrix inhibitor precursors. A commercial 8H Thornel T-300 3K satin weave, which was used as matrix reinforcement, was purchased from Amoco, Inc. The fiber density was 1.78 g/cm³, tensile strength 3.806 GPa, and modulus 232 GPa. Aerocarb 80 petroleum pitch produced by Ashland Petroleum Co. was used as a matrix material. Particulate matrix inhibitors employed in this study were purchased from Alfa and Johnson Matthey, Inc. Average particle size of boron and boron carbide powders was below 1 micron and zirconium boride powder below 44 microns (-325 mesh).

2.2. Fabrication of Matrix Inhibited C-C Composites

The overall fabrication procedure involved preparation of prepregs and preforms followed by heat treatment in order to stabilize and carbonize the structure of C-C composites. All particulate matrix inhibitors employed in this study were purchased in the form of fine powders and were used without further grinding. The Aerocarb 80 pitch was ground prior to mixing with particulate inhibitor powders.

Prepregs were formed using woven carbon fiber cloth and a mixture of particulate matrix inhibitors with pitch powder. First, rectangular sheets of carbon fiber cloth (8.5" X 8.5") were cut and laid on stainless steel metal plates. The mixture of pitch and inhibitor precursors was then uniformly spread over each carbon fiber cloth sheet. The pitch/powder formulations used in this study are summarized in Table 1. Fabricated composites incorporated the following formulations of fine powders: boron (composite B(1) and B(2)), zirconium boride and boron (composite C), and boron carbide (composites D(1) through D(4)). Heat treatment was performed under an inert atmosphere of nitrogen at 400°C for 50 hours.

Preforms were fabricated using prepregs and a hot-press molding technique. First, prepregs were trimmed to the dimensions of 8 in. X 8 in. before being laid up in stacks, six prepregs to a stack, prior to hot press molding. The molding conditions employed were as follows: temperatures in the range of 350°C to 400°C and a pressure of 0.28 to 0.55 MPa.

2.3. Oxidation Stabilization and Carbonization

Hot-pressed preforms were stabilized by heating in pure oxygen. Preform specimens (2" X 4" in size) were kept isothermally at 200°C in oxygen flowing at a rate of 80 sccm for 50 hours. Stabilized specimens were subsequently carbonized in nitrogen at 1000°C at a heating rate of 10°C/hour.

2.4. Microstructural Characterization of Matrix Inhibited C-C Composites and Oxidation Testing

The overall morphological information such as the size, shape and distribution of composite constituents as well as macrocracks and macropores was studied via polarized light optical microscopy (ORM) using a Nikon Microphot optical microscope. Elemental analysis of selected regions of C-C composite specimens was performed using energy dispersive x-ray spectrometry (EDS) attached to an Hitachi S-800 high resolution scanning electron microscope. This unit was equipped with a LaB₆ electron source and minicomputer-controlled electron beam scanning and EDX LINK data acquisition system. Oxidation tests were performed using a horizontal tube furnace.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Fabrication of Matrix Inhibited C-C Composites

Seven matrix inhibited C-C composite preforms were fabricated using a variety of pitch/powder mixture formulations (see Table 1). The amounts of matrix inhibitor precursors added to each pitch matrix comprised between 2 and 20 weight percent of the total composite weight. Each composite specimen was carefully examined at various stages of the fabrication process. During the prepreg preparation the pitch/powder mixtures of B(2), C, and D(1) through D(3) spread uniformly over the entire surface of each carbon fiber cloth sheet and a substantial amount of pitch impregnated each sheet. The viscosity of mixture B(1) and D(4) on the other hand was very high and consequently spread only over the center part of the carbon fiber cloths. In addition, only partial infiltration was achieved. Prepregs fabricated with mixture D(4) were subsequently used to produce preforms. Pitch /powder mixture B(1) did not bond with the boron powder; therefore this formulation was abandoned.

All remaining pitch/powder formulations with the exception of D(4) produced well infiltrated preforms. Preform D(4) was infiltrated only in its center with the edges of the carbon fiber cloth dry. There was no observable delamination however. Weight changes observed during oxidative stabilization and carbonization are listed in Table 2 along with final densities and thicknesses of heat treated specimens. The densities of the composites were determined as bulk densities (i.e., by the weight and dimension method).

3.2. Microstructural Investigations of Nonoxidized Composites

Figures 1 and 2 show examples of optical micrographs of the structure of matrix inhibited C-C composites C, D(1), and D(4) fabricated using the prepreg-preform technique described earlier in this paper. All specimens

exhibited an appreciable porosity which was also reflected by the low values of densities which ranged from 1.34 g/cm³ for composite D(4) to 1.51 g/cm³ for composite C (Table 2). Figure 1 shows an interfacial region (fiber-matrix) within composite C. Zirconium boride particles with sizes up to 25 microns are distributed within the predominantly isotropic interbundular matrix (area A, Fig. 1) and are located very close to the longitudinal fiber bundle (area B, Fig. 1). The macrostructure of intrabundular regions on the other hand are mostly anisotropic (area C, Fig. 1). Microstructure of composites D(1) and D(4) doped with submicron size particles of boron carbide is shown in Figure 2. The interbundular matrix of composite D(1) (see Figure 2a) is predominantly isotropic with small mesophasic spheres present. These are characteristic of an early stages of mesophase formation (area A, Fig. 2). The intrabundular matrix is anisotropic (area C, Fig. 2). Similar microstructural features were found in composite D(4), Figure 2b, with the exception of the interbundular matrix which is almost entirely isotropic.

The detailed distribution of particulate matrix inhibitors within C-C composites was studied using EDS techniques. Figure 3 shows examples of EDS distribution maps of zirconium and boron in sections of composites C and D(3) respectively along with SEM micrographs of the same areas. It is evident that the inhibitor particles which are distributed mostly in the interbundle area of the inhibited composite, form bands along the interfaces of fiber bundles. High concentrations and clusters of inhibitor particles are found in these areas in contrast to the very few inhibitor particles found within the fiber bundles.

3.3. Oxidation Behavior of Matrix Inhibited C-C Composites

The results of preliminary isothermal oxidation tests performed in dry static air at 800°C are summarized in Figure 4. A 2-D, uninhibited, graphitized, pitch matrix C-C composite was used as a comparison. Composite specimens D(2), D(3), and D(4) show initially a slight weight gain due to oxide formation followed by steady weight loss during approximately the first four hours of the oxidation run (Figure 4). After 4-5 hours the oxidation rate slightly increases. Specimens D(1), D(2), and D(3) show a very similar pattern of weight change until accumulating a weight loss of approximately 2% of their weights after six hours. Specimen D(4), on the contrary, underwent faster gasification rate and lost 5% of its initial weight during six hours of oxidation. Weight losses of composites in series B and C are much higher than all composites in series D, see Figure 4.

3.4. Microstructural Investigations of Oxidized Composites

Results of microstructural investigations of matrix inhibited C-C composites oxidized in dry air at 800°C are presented in Figures 5 and 6. Figure 5 is a SEM micrograph of the surface of oxidized composite C which lost 40% of its initial weight. A deep surface hole (position A, Figure 5a) is surrounded by longitudinal (position B) and cross sectional (position C) surface fiber bundles. The top surface, as well as the surface of the hole, are extensively covered with glass. A higher magnification micrograph (Figure 5b) shows the surface of a longitudinal bundle of the same oxidized composite. One can observe an irregular surface consisting of a large number of particles embedded in a glassy coating. The appearance of the surface of inhibited and oxidized composite D(3) is depicted in Figure 6. A SEM micrograph of Figure 6a shows an interbundular area of the surface in the vicinity of open surface porosity (position A). Longitudinal (position B) and cross sectional (position C) fiber bundles as well as interbundular matrix pockets (position D) are covered with a glassy phase. Detailed analysis of the same specimen at higher magnification reveals a very smooth glassy phase enveloping carbon fibers, Figure 6b. Although SEM results of oxidized composites C and D(3) indicate presence of a substantial amount of glass on their surfaces, corresponding oxidation results show that composite C was not protected against oxidation as well as composite D(3). Thus, other factors such as spreading of borate glass over fiber surfaces, its viscosity, and particle size of particulate inhibitor precursors have to be also considered in an attempt to explain observed differences in oxidation performance of these composites.

4. CONCLUSIONS

1. Particulate matrix inhibitors are distributed mostly in the interbundle area of matrix inhibited composites and form bands along interbundle interfaces. Clusters of high concentrations of inhibitor particles were found in these areas in contrast to very few inhibitor particles found within the fiber bundles. There is a good bonding between interbundular matrix doped with inhibitors and fiber bundles and there is no delamination.
2. Regions of the interbundle matrix of C-C composites in which high concentrations of particulate matrix inhibitors are isotropic. Composites with lower particulate inhibitor loadings, i.e. composites B(2), C, D(1), D(2), and D(3) consist also of regions of matrix which are only partially transformed into mesophase.

3. Composite D(4) inhibited with submicron size powder of boron carbide shows the lowest weight loss during isothermal oxidation in static air at 800°C. Composite C, which is inhibited with coarser powder of zirconium boride, shows the highest weight loss under the same oxidation conditions despite the presence of considerable amount of glass covering its surface after oxidation. It has been concluded that the particle size and nonuniform particle distribution of zirconium boride powder are amongst others responsible for the observed oxidation behavior of tested specimens.

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BIOGRAPHY

Pawel Tlomak is a research associate at Materials Technology Center (MTC) at Southern Illinois University at Carbondale (SIU). He received his M.S. degree in solid state physics from the University of Wroclaw, Poland in 1975 and his Ph.D. degree in Materials Science and Engineering from SIU in 1988. He has been employed at MTC since 1988 and conducted research on fabrication, characterization, and oxidation protection of C-C composites. He has recently received a research grant to investigate oxidation resistance of matrix inhibited C-C composites.

TABLE 1. Matrix Inhibited Composite Formulations

Composites	Fiber [wt %]	Matrix [wt %]	Inhibitor [wt %]
B (1)	50	40	10
B (2)	50	48	2
C	50	40	10
D (1)	40	52	8
D (2)	40	48	12
D (3)	40	44	16
D (4)	40	40	20

TABLE 2. Properties of Matrix Inhibited Composites

Sample	Weight Change [%]		Density [g/cm ³]	Thickness [mm]
	Stabilization	Carbonization		
B(2)	+3.99	-8.56	1.40	2.75
C	+3.65	-8.23	1.51	2.75
D (1)	+3.97	-10.43	1.41	3.15
D (2)	+3.92	-9.63	1.40	3.23
D (3)	+3.70	-9.04	1.40	3.60
D (4)	+3.66	-8.48	1.34	3.65

Figure 1. Optical micrograph showing section of composite C: (A) interbundle matrix filled with particles of zirconium boride, (B) longitudinal fiber bundle, and (C) intrabundle area. Arrows show individual particles of zirconium boride.

Figure 2a. Optical micrograph showing section of composite D(1): (A) interbundle matrix filled with particles of boron carbide, (B) longitudinal fiber bundle, and (C) intrabundle area. Arrows show areas of high concentrations of inhibitor particles.

Figure 2b. Optical micrograph showing section of composite D(4): (A) interbundle matrix filled with particles of boron carbide, (B) longitudinal fiber bundle, and (C) intrabundle area. Inhibitor particles are uniformly distributed throughout interbundle matrix.

Figure 3a. SEM micrograph and EDS distribution of zirconium in C-C composite C.

Figure 3b. SEM micrograph and EDS distribution of boron in C-C composite D(3).

Figure 4. Weight changes as function of time for the series of matrix inhibited C-C composites fabricated in this study.

Figure 5. Appearance of the surface of oxidized matrix inhibited C-C composite C after 40% burnoff at 800°C. Part (a): (A) open surface porosity, (B) longitudinal fiber bundle, and (C) cross sectional fiber bundle. Part (b) is a surface of an longitudinal bundle at higher magnification.

Figure 6. Appearance of the surface of oxidized matrix inhibited C-C composite D(3) after 35% burnoff at 800°C. Part (a): (A) open surface porosity, (B) longitudinal fiber bundle, (C) cross sectional fiber bundle, and (D) interbundle matrix. Part (b) is a surface of an longitudinal fiber bundle at higher magnification.

